

LAMINATED COMPOSITES UNDER IMPACT LOADING

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It is well-known that the brittleness, or lack of impact resistance capability, of the modern composites is a major obstacle for its application. In predicting the impact induced stress in a composite, the lamination theory is an indispensable tool. For transient problems, the validity of the lamination theory has not been proved. It is the purpose of the present paper to demonstrate the accuracy of the lamination theory in transient wave propagation problems.

Impact experiments were conducted with composite material plates and the strain histories at various points on the plate were recorded. These strains were compared with theoretical calculation based on equations derived from a lamination theory and a method of characteristic numerical computer program.

Two plate specimens, 609.6mm x 355.6mm, were used, each consisted of 50 layers of graphite/epoxy; one a cross-ply laminate, and the other a $0^{\circ}/\pm 45^{\circ}$ angle-ply laminate. A pendulum impact system was used for two types of impact; an inplane impact and a shear-bending impact.

The governing equations utilized in this study were those of the Whitney and Pagano laminated plate theory. A computer code, based on the method of characteristics, was used to solve the governing equations.

Based on our study, we have concluded that the lamination theory adequately predicts the wave velocities and transient strains in symmetric cross-ply and angle-ply graphite epoxy plates.

Introduction

Modern high performance composite materials have been considered seriously for application to the jet engine fan blade. The materials must be able to resist the impact due to ingested foreign objects such as birds, ice, and stones. Due to the complexity of the geometry of the blade, detailed fiber-by-fiber, or ply-by-ply, "micro-mechanic" stress analysis is not feasible at this time; laminated plate theory must be used to account only for the integrated effect over the layers. The purpose of this paper is to demonstrate the accuracy of the equations derived from lamination theory by comparing experimental results with those calculated from these equations.

The laminated plate equations used in this paper are those derived by Whitney and Pagano (1). As discussed in Ref.(2), this set of equations is more accurate than that of Ref.(3), and may be considered as a representative "first order" laminated plate theory. Several analytical and numerical solutions to the laminated plate equations have been presented recently. Wang and Tuckmantel (4), and Moon (5) have discussed the wave surfaces based on the laminated plate equations due to abrupt change in stress. Chow (6) applied the Laplace transform technique and calculated the deflection of a laminated plate under the concentrated load. Moon (7) solved the problem of one-dimensional wave propagation due to a prescribed line load by the fast Fourier transform technique.

Very little experimental results appear in the literature. Whittier and Peck (8) measured the response due to impact and studied the dispersion of the wave in unbounded layered media, not a laminated plate. Similarly, in References (9-10) ultrasonic methods are used to study dispersion and to measure effective elastic constants of unbounded composites. There has been no direct measurement of transient strain histories of laminated plates subjected to realistic impact loading.

In this paper, experimental measurements were made and compared with calculations from the laminated plate equations. The experimental phase consisted of impacting the edge of the specimen plate with a striker plate. The experiment was designed to permit measurements of a one-dimensional wave propagation in the specimen. The velocity of the impact was maintained at a low level such that the response is purely elastic. The duration of the resulting impact was controlled by varying the striker plate length in the direction normal to the impacted edge. The strain histories were monitored along the mid-width of the specimen. These strain histories were used for comparison with the analytically predicted wave velocities and strains. Additional gages were mounted on the plate specimens to monitor simultaneity of impact and uniformity of strains across the plate thickness as the wave propagates into the plate. Two specimen plates fabricated from graphite-epoxy were tested; one of cross-ply lay-up and the other of angle-plys. Each specimen was

subjected to two separate impact loadings; an inplane impact and a shear-bending impact. In addition, similar impacts were conducted on aluminum specimens, not presented here, to ascertain the accuracy of the experimental set-up, since wave propagation in aluminum structures is reasonably well understood.

The analytical phase of this study consists of solving the Whitney and Pagano equation by the method of characteristics. For inplane impacts, the striker was of identical material as the specimen, the loading pulse is considered to be of rectangular shape of known amplitude. For shear-bending impacts an approximate loading condition for the specimen was derived; it involves matching deflection and forces between the striker and the specimen at the contact line; the wave propagation in the striker is also taken into consideration.

Experimental Procedure

A pendulum impact system was used for the experimental work. The concept of this technique is simply that of attaching a striker plate to a pendulum arm, which is attached by a bearing to an A-frame, raising the pendulum a specific height, releasing the pendulum, and allowing the striker plate to impact the specimen. The striker and specimen were aligned to assure simultaneous contact. The rectangular specimen plate was clamped to the far edge, free at the impact edge and the two sides. The specimen was horizontal for inplane impact, and vertical for shear-bending impact. The dimensions of the specimen and the striker are shown in Fig. 1. The striker plate was raised to a certain height by a string, which was burned to initiate the striking motion. The contact of the striker plate and the specimen triggered the oscilloscopes. Figure 2 is a photograph of this pendulum impact system with the specimen in a horizontal position.

The striker plate velocity measurements were obtained by passing a tab, attached to the striker assembly, between a light source and a photodiode system immediately before impact. Interrupting the light source resulted in a voltage change which was measurable on the scope. By measuring the distance between the three photodiodes and the elapsed time between voltage peaks on the oscilloscope, an accurate velocity measurement can be obtained.

Laminated Plate Specimen

The plate specimens were fabricated from 3501/AS graphite epoxy prepreg 304.8mm tape. The first specimen consisted of 50 layers with a total thickness of cured plate of 8.26mm, and layed up as a $[(0^{\circ}_2/90^{\circ})_8/0^{\circ}]_5$ cross-ply laminate; the other consisted of 50 layers with a total cured plate thickness of 7.11mm and a $[(0^{\circ}/45^{\circ}/0^{\circ}/-45^{\circ})_6/0^{\circ}]_5$ angle-ply lay-up.

Values of the longitudinal Young's modulus and the major Poisson's ratio of the lamina were measured from coupon tests, they are $E_1 = 122 \text{ KN/mm}^2$, and $\nu_{12} = 0.30$. The measured density was $\sigma = 0.00151 \text{ gm/mm}^3$. The value of the transverse Young's modulus was estimated from data supplied by the manufacturer, Hercules Incorporated, which was $E_2 = 8.96 \text{ KN/mm}^2$.

The dimension of the specimen, as shown in Fig. 1, was selected to be wide enough so that unloading waves emanating from the free side edges would not interfere with the main one-dimensional pulse as it propagated along the center line of the specimen.

The gage locations for the tests are also shown in Fig. 1. Gages 2, 4, and 5 were used to measure the simultaneity of each impact. Perfect simultaneity of impact would produce identical strain traces (arrival time, shape, and magnitude) at each of these three gages. Gages 2 and 2R, where 2R is directly below 2, were used to detect through-thickness bending caused by the impact. Gages 1, 2, and 3, were used to measure wave velocities and strain histories of the main one-dimensional pulse as it propagates through these locations on the plate.

The strain gages used were of the open-faced general purpose foil type, 3.175mm in length, and were mounted with M-Bond 200 adhesive. Ellis BAM-1B bridge amplifiers were used to provide calibration settings of $400 \mu\text{m/m}$ /major division. A Tektronix time-mark generator type 184 was used in conjunction with their type 565 Dual Beam Oscilloscope to provide an accurate time base of 20 μsec /major division for wave speed calculations. Two 4-channel type 3A74 beam splitters were used to obtain the six individual traces on one picture from the strain gages.

Numerical Calculation

For symmetric cross-ply, or angle-ply, laminated plates under one-dimensional inplane impact, the governing equations of (1) reduce to

$$A_{11} u_{,xx}^0 = P u_{,tt}^0 \quad (1)$$

where x represents the spatial coordinate in the direction of wave propagation, t the time coordinate, u^0 the mid-plane displacements in the x -directions, and P the plate mass term. A comma denotes differentiation with respect to the variables following it. This is a simple wave equation with wave velocity $c_0 = (A_{11}/P)^{1/2}$. For a finite length striker plate of the same material as the specimen, the response in the specimen is simply a rectangular wave of amplitude $\epsilon_0 = V_0/2 c_0$ (where ϵ_0 is the strain and V_0 the initial velocity of the striker) and of a pulse length $t_0 = 2\ell/c_0$, where ℓ is the length of the striker.

For symmetrically layed-up plates under one-dimensional transverse shear-bending impact, the governing equations without surface tractions reduce to

$$k A_{55} (\psi_{x,x} + w_{,xx}) = P w_{,tt} \quad (2)$$

$$D_{11} \psi_{x,xx} + D_{16} \psi_{y,xx} - k A_{55} (\psi_x + w_{,x}) = I \psi_{x,tt} \quad (3)$$

$$D_{16} \psi_{x,xx} + D_{66} \psi_{y,xx} - k A_{44} \psi_y = I \psi_{y,tt} \quad (4)$$

The variables w , ψ_x , and ψ_y are coupled in these equations; ψ_x and ψ_y are strongly coupled together by Eqns. (3) and (4), and w weakly coupled to the other two through Eq. (2). This is a set of totally hyperbolic partial differential equations, and are solved by a numerical method of characteristic code, MCDU-22, (11).

For symmetric cross-ply plates, D_{16} vanishes, and Eq. (4) uncouples from the other two; ψ_y is independent of ψ_x and w , and is not excited by the one-dimensional impact. The other two equations (2) and (3) are only weakly coupled together, and are solved by a more convenient method of characteristic code, MCDU-21, (12).

The loading function for the specimen in the transverse impact case depends on the wave motion in the striker and cannot be specified explicitly beforehand. Instead, the wave motions in the striker and the specimen are solved simultaneously, with certain matching conditions at the contact interface. The striker is assumed to have pure inplane motion, governed by the simple wave equation. The motion of the entire specimen plate is assumed to be in the shear-bending mode where the three-dimensional compression waves in the region close to the impact surface have been neglected.

The three second order differential equations, Eqs. (2), (3), and (4), require three boundary conditions at the impacted edge, $x=0$, (13). The simple wave equation of the striker needs one boundary condition at $z=0$, where the wave motion in the plate is along x -direction and in the striker along negative z -direction, as shown in Fig. 3. The four required boundary conditions are supplied at the impact surface $x=0$, $z=0$, by (a) matching the displacements of the striker and the plate, (b) equating the total axial force in the striker to the total shear force in the plate, (c) assuming the moment for the plate is equal to the force in the striker multiplied by half the striker thickness, and (d) assuming the moment M_{xy} is zero. If $\sigma(z,t)$ and $u(z,t)$ are the stress and displacement in the striker, then, these conditions are,

$$u(0,t) = w(0,t) \quad (5)$$

$$\sigma(0,t) = Q_x(0,t)/b \quad (6)$$

$$M_x(0,t) = \sigma(0,t) b^2/2 \quad (7)$$

$$M_{xy}(0,t) = 0 \quad (8)$$

where Q_x , M_x , and M_{xy} are the shear force and moments in the plate.

Before the leading discontinuous wave front in the striker reflects back from the tail end of the striker, the stress $\sigma(0,t)$ can be solved from the striker equation and the jump in velocity, or, for $0 < t < 2l/c$.

$$\frac{1}{b} Q_x(0,t) = -\sigma c_0 [V_0 - w_t(0,t)] \quad (9)$$

In deriving this, Eqns. (5) and (6) have been utilized; the three Eqns. (7), (8), and (9) form a set of proper boundary conditions for the specimen Eqns. (2), (3), and (4), and are no longer coupled explicitly with the striker equation.

For $t > 2l/c_0$, if the stress at the interface becomes zero, or positive, the striker and the specimen separate, the matching condition must be replaced by free edge conditions, and the subsequent motion of the specimen can be solved directly, independent of the striker. If the striker and the specimen are still in contact, then Eqns. (1) to (8) must be solved simultaneously.

Comparison of Results

Inplane Impacts

Typical results from the strain histories monitored on the cross-ply laminated plate under inplane impact are shown in Fig 4. The strain gage numbers are shown to the right of the photographs. Observation of the strain histories from gages 2, 4, and 5 show that good simultaneity of impact has been achieved. The maximum difference between wave arrival times at the three gages was approximately 6 μ sec; the magnitudes of the strain pulse at each of these three gages were nearly identical. Gages 2 and 2R demonstrate that little bending was induced by this inplane impact. The average wave velocity (7.71 mm/ μ sec) measured from the first disturbance at gages 1, 2, and 3 agrees with the theoretical velocity of 7.55 mm/ μ sec, with $A_{11} = 0.713$ MN/mm and $P = 0.0125$ gm/mm² for the laminated specimen. These three gages also show that the initial pulse has little attenuation or dispersion.

Comparisons of the experimental and analytically predicted strain histories are shown in Fig. 5. The analytical response is a rectangular wave of a pulse duration 20.19 μ sec, and a strain amplitude of 160 μ mm/mm, which is based on an impact velocity of $V_0 = 2.423$ m/sec.

Observation of Fig. 5 shows that the strain magnitudes of the experimental and analytical results are in good agreement. The average experimental pulse duration was 35 μ sec as compared to the theoretical value of 20.19 μ sec. Much of this difference is due to the delay in the strain gage circuit response. The experimental shape is approximately that of a sine squared; the deviation from the rectangular shape is to be expected since the strain gages cannot measure discontinuities in loading or unloading.

Strain gages readings (not shown here) for the angle-ply plate under inplane impact indicate that good simultaneity of impact has also been achieved. Gages 2 and 2R demonstrate that little bending was induced. The average measured wave velocity of 7.54 mm/ μ sec agrees well with the theoretical velocity of 7.39 mm/ μ sec, with $A_{11} = 0.584$ MN/mm and $P = 0.0107$ gm/mm². The strain histories are shown in Fig. 6. The impact velocity is $V_0 = 2.55$ m/sec, which yields theoretical pulse duration of 20.62, μ sec., and a strain of 173 μ mm/mm. As is in the cross-ply case, the magnitude of the experimental and analytical strain pulse agree well, while the pulse duration and shape do not.

Transverse Shear-Bending Impact

Figure 7 presents typical results from the strain histories on the cross-ply laminate produced by the transverse shear-bending impact. The trace numbers again refer to the strain gages number in Fig. 1. At least four impact tests with almost identical strain history traces were obtained for each impact case. Again the strain histories from gages 2, 4, and 5 show that good simultaneity of impact was achieved. The maximum difference between wave arrival times at these three gages was approximately 5 μ sec; except for gage 4, the magnitudes of the strain pulse at these gages were found to be essentially identical. The reason for the slight discrepancy in the magnitude at gage 4 is that, at the impact surface, uniform contact during the impact was not achieved, because of minute ripples on the surface of the laminate. For instance, for an impact speed of 2.5 m/sec, a 0.0254mm(0.001") irregularity on the impact surface causes a 10 μ sec discrepancy in arrival time. Gages 2 and 2R demonstrate that near perfect bending was induced by the impact.

The laminated plate properties are calculated from lamina properties and are listed in Table I. The striker velocity V_0 was 2.55 m/sec. The average wave velocity determined from the peak strain at gages 1, 2, and 3 was 1.67 mm/ μ sec, which is much closer to the theoretical shear velocity of 1.53 mm/ μ sec, than the theoretical bending velocity of 7.69 mm/ μ sec, indicating that the pulse is primarily a shear wave. There is some uncertainty about the measured shear wave speed. For instance, if measured from the first disturbance at the gages, the shear velocity would be 1.81 mm/ μ sec.

Figure 8 shows that the pulse shape and magnitude of the experimental results are in general agreement with those from the theoretical calculation. The analytical strain at 25.4mm contains a precursor bending wave travelling with the plate wave velocity, as indicated by the abrupt wave front. (The precursor at 127mm is not plotted) The strain gage did not pick up this precursor, probably due to its limitation in frequency response. However, the fact that the bulk of the energy is travelling with a velocity nearly equal to the shear velocity is evident.

Results of the angle-ply specimen subjected to transverse impact are shown in Fig. 9. The striker impact velocity V_0 is 2.55 m/sec. The average of the measured wave velocities, based on first disturbance at gages 1,2, and 3 was 2.11 mm/ μ sec. The average velocity based on peak strain was 1.39 mm/ μ sec. The theoretical shear velocity for the angle ply was computed to be 1.58 mm/ μ sec. The agreement between the theoretical and experimental shear velocities is not as good as that in the inplane velocity, c_0 . The shape and magnitude of the pulses, however, do show fairly good agreement.

For both the cross-ply and angle-ply specimens, the striker separated from the specimen after $t > t_0$, which simplified the calculation.

Conclusion

Based on the comparison between experimental and theoretical results, we conclude that the laminated plate theory used here adequately predicts the wave velocities and transient strains in symmetric cross-ply and angle-ply composite plates under either inplane impact, or transverse shear-bending impact. The wave length to plate thickness ratio for the results reported here, is approximately 20. Experimental results with 25.4 mm striker, which are not reported here, indicate that if the wave length to plate thickness ratio is larger than eight, the laminated plate theory is satisfactory for practical purposes.

Nomenclature

- A_{ij}, D_{ij}, I - plate coefficients and plate mass terms as defined in Ref. 1.
 k - shear correction constant
 w - plate deflection
 ψ_x, ψ_y - rotations

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Table I. Graphite/Epoxy Laminated Plate Properties

Lay-up	Cross-ply	Angle-ply
σ (10^{-3} gm/mm ³)	$[(0_2^0/90^0)_8/0^0]_S$	$[(0^0/45^0/0^0/-45^0)_6,0^0]_S$
A_{11} (MN/mm)	1.511	1.511
A_{55} (MN/mm)	0.713	0.584
A_{44} (MN/mm)	0.0294	0.0269
D_{11} (MN-mm)	-	0.0267
D_{16} (MN-mm)	4.19	2.49
D_{66} (MN-mm)	0	-0.0491
c_0 (mm/ μ sec)	-	0.506
	7.55	7.39

1. Specimen Geometry and Gage Locations.

EXPERIMENTAL IMPACT SYSTEM

2. Photograph of Pendulum Impact System

3. Shear-Bending Impact Geometry

20 μ sec./div. horizontal
187 μ mm/mm/div. vertical
STRIKER VELOCITY = 2.423 m/sec.

4. Typical Oscilloscope Traces for the Cross-Ply Plate.

5. Theoretical and Experimental Inplane Strain Response of the Cross-Ply Plate.

6. Theoretical and Experimental Inplane Strain Response of the Angle-Ply Plate. (Trace numbers refer to gages shown in Fig. 1.

40 μ sec./div. horizontal
400 μ mm/mm/div. vertical

7. Typical Oscilloscope Traces for Cross-Ply Laminate Subjected to Transverse Shear-Bending Impact.

8. Theoretical and Experimental Strain Response of the Cross-Ply Laminate Due to Transverse (Shear-Bending) Impact.

9. Theoretical and Experimental Strain Response of Angle-Ply Laminate Due to Transverse (Shear-Bending) Impact.